

BRIDGING AUTHENTICATION FOR SERVICES IN THE VIRTUAL RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT

Aug 2025

AUTHOR(S):

Tomas Ondrejka

Technical University of Denmark (DTU)

SUPERVISOR(S):

Enrique García García (IT-TC-LCG)

Giovanni Guerrieri (IT-TC-LCG)

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ABSTRACT

Scientific workflows span heterogeneous infrastructures and institutions, demanding secure, interoperable, and reproducible access. This project consolidates identity handling for the ESCAPE Virtual Research Environment and REANA by adopting standards-based authentication and authorization, unifying access on token-based mechanisms, and clarifying system responsibilities. The design yields a stateless architecture that integrates cleanly with standard identity providers, enhancing maintainability and deployment portability.

1 Introduction

Scientific analyses operate at scale, requiring coordinated data access, workflow execution, and reproducibility across diverse resources. The ESCAPE project [1] (European Science Cluster of Astronomy and Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures) developed open-source tools and services for data-driven research across scientific domains. Within this framework, the Virtual Research Environment (VRE)[2] is a cloud-based, collaborative platform at CERN for European scientific communities. In this context, **REANA** [3] provides reusable, declarative workflow execution on remote compute backends, enabling analyses to be specified once and run reproducibly across infrastructures.

Despite its functional maturity, REANA's identity layer remained fragmented, increasing integration effort and limiting interoperability. This work streamlines REANA's stack by adopting authentication and authorization standards, **OAuth 2.0**[4] and **OpenID Connect**[5], unifying access through a single token model, and clearly separating responsibilities so that authentication is client-driven and the server focuses solely on authorization. The resulting design reduces operational complexity and enables multi-institutional use.

2 Authentication Concepts

2.1 IdP

An Identity Provider (IdP) is a trusted entity that creates, maintains, and manages user identities and provides authentication to relying applications (the relying parties).

In practice, most Identity Providers implement OAuth 2.0 for delegated authorization and extend it with OpenID Connect for an identity layer; after successful authentication, they issue a JSON Web Token (JWT) with cryptographically signed claims about the subject. For example, the ESCAPE INDIGO IAM service [6] adopts this model, relying on OAuth 2.0, OIDC, and JWTs for identity and access management.

Token issuance is a core IdP function. Tokens, typically JWTs, carry claims such, and optional attributes (e.g., roles, groups), enabling stateless, interoperable authentication and authorization without shared session state. In this work, the focus is on ESCAPE IAM, which issues OAuth 2.0/OIDC-compliant JWTs for the ESCAPE Virtual Research Environment, and on CERN's Single Sign-On (SSO).

2.2 OAuth 2.0

OAuth 2.0 is an open standard for delegated authorization that lets a resource owner grant a third-party client controlled access to protected assets, without sharing credentials. The framework defines four roles: Resource Owner, Client, Authorization Server, and Resource Server; it also supports multiple flows for web, native, and limited-input environments.

Relevant flows in this work are:

- **Authorization code flow:** an intermediate code is exchanged for an access token.
- **Device code flow:** designed for devices or CLI tools; the client obtains a device and user code, instructs the user to visit a verification URL on another device, and polls until the access token is issued [7].

OAuth 2.0 includes scope-based authorization (restricting token privileges), token-based access control (presenting tokens in HTTP requests, typically via the Authorization header),

and protocol layering (authentication added via OpenID Connect). In this project, OAuth 2.0 underpins acquisition and use of JWT access tokens issued by ESCAPE IAM, ensuring secure, interoperable, and JWT-aware access to REANA services across web and command-line interfaces.

2.3 OpenID

OpenID Connect (OIDC) is an identity layer atop OAuth 2.0 that adds standardized authentication, allowing clients to verify end-user identity and obtain profile information in an interoperable, REST-style manner. After successful authentication, the IdP issues an ID Token, typically a signed JWT, containing claims, authentication time, and optionally name or email; this ID Token is returned alongside the OAuth 2.0 access token.

OIDC also defines two key endpoints. The UserInfo endpoint is a protected resource that returns standardized end-user claims when presented with an access token. The OpenID Provider Configuration document (e.g. escape.cloud.cnaf.infn.it/.well-known/openid-configuration) describes the IdP's capabilities, supported flows, endpoints, signing keys via the JSON Web Key Set (JWKS) URI, and supported claims, enabling dynamic client discovery and configuration.

2.4 JWT

A JSON Web Token is a compact, URL-safe representation of claims used widely in OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect to convey authentication and authorization data statelessly. A JWT comprises three base64url-encoded segments: header, payload, and signature, concatenated with dots.

Two standard JWT claims are central to identity mapping and authorization (`sub` – user id within IdP, `iss` – token IdP itself). Depending on context, different token types are issued: an ID Token carrying identity claims (e.g., `sub`, `name`, `email`); an Access Token for protected resource access (may include authorization claims, scopes, and expiry); and a Refresh Token, long-lived and used to obtain new access tokens.

JWT Verification keys are published by the IdP via a JWKS, discoverable at the `jwtks_uri` advertised in the `.well-known/openid-configuration` endpoint of an IdP server.

3 Goals

3.1 Adoption of OAuth 2.0 / OIDC Standards

Adopting OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect as REANA's authentication/authorization foundation aligns the system with industry standards, enabling interoperability with institutional and federated IdPs under established trust frameworks and mature security models. Compliance spans standardized flows, claim sets, and discovery, ensuring consistent IdP interaction and straightforward integration by external services without bespoke logic. This eases client integration, and maintains compatibility across diverse identity stacks.

3.2 Removal of Invenio Authentication Components

Removing Invenio-based authentication components reduces architectural complexity, and database overhead. It is currently significant, with roughly half of the schema devoted to `auth/authz`

tables that Invenio maintains alongside endpoints and token storage. Delegating identity management to trusted IdPs streamlines REANA to its core purpose, yielding a smaller and more maintainable architecture.

3.3 Unified JWT-Based Access Across All Interfaces

Originally, REANA relied on a mix of custom REANA tokens, GitLab tokens, and Flask session IDs, with Invenio sitting in the middle to manage these credentials and their mappings. This fragmented setup meant that different interfaces depended on different tokens. By moving to a single IdP-issued JWT, these layers are unified: the same token can be used across the web UI, CLI, and automation. Invenio is no longer required to mediate identities, and the flow simplifies to direct JWT validation against the trusted IdP, yielding a coherent and lightweight access-control model.

3.4 Stateless and Scalable Authorization Model

A stateless authorization model places all authentication and authorization data in a JWT issued by a trusted Identity Provider, removing the need for shared session storage or auth users. Any REANA server instance can validate and authorize requests, simplifying the architecture and improving fault tolerance

3.5 Foundation for Scope-Based Authorization

Establishing a claim- and scope-aware authorization framework prepares REANA for advanced models such as Role-based access control (RBAC) and scope-based permissions. Relevant claims, roles, group memberships, and granted scopes, are extracted from JWTs issued by trusted IdPs and used to enforce policies that govern per-user access to resources and operations.

3.6 Clarification of REANA Server Identity Responsibilities

Posing a clear separation of concerns for REANA's identity management results in the delegation of authentication to trusted Identity Providers, while keeping authorization as a core server responsibility.

4 Architecture and Implementation

4.1 REANA Server Auth Responsibility Model

In the prior design (Figure 1), REANA Server contained authentication redirects, handled callbacks/code exchange, managed sessions, and exposed authentication endpoints. As shown in Figure 2, the new model enables device code flows in environments without a graphical UI, significantly reducing complexity and therefore lowering latency.

The REANA Server is restricted to authorization, while authentication is initiated by the user (browser/CLI) and performed directly against an IdP using OAuth 2.0/OIDC.

The IdP issues a JWT to the client, which is presented to REANA; the server validates the signature via JWKS, checks key claims, and enforces authorization based on identity and roles, remaining agnostic to the token acquisition method.

Figure 1: Previous REANA Server Auth Architecture

Figure 2: New REANA Server Auth Architecture

4.2 JWT Validation in the REANA Server

Authlib [8] has been selected for the project as it provides well-supported OAuth 2.0, OIDC, JWT, and JWK utilities, to underpin token validation while minimizing code churn. Rather than replacing existing hooks, we layered JWT authorization on the current design using a decorator that differentiates token types. The `reana-server` module extracts the Bearer token, retrieves IdP JWKS, and verifies the JWT signature and decodes the payload; then resolves the user by IdP identity (e.g., `idp_id`), performs JIT provisioning when necessary, and finally enforces authorization.

4.3 Mapping IdP Identities to REANA Users

REANA currently auto-generates user IDs that lack any reference to the IdP user, yet identity extraction relies on JWT claims, specifically the IdP user identifier in `sub` (and the issuer in `iss`).

With the removal of the Invenio package, the previous IdP-to-REANA user ID mappings are no longer used, therefore identity resolution relies directly on the JWT claims. Two options were considered: creating a separate mapping table for (`sub`, `iss`) or adding `sub` and `iss` columns to the existing user table. The latter was selected for simplicity, acknowledging that a future multi-IdP setup would demand a more complex implementation (e.g., support for multiple trusted IdPs and verification against multiple JWK key sets).

4.4 Just-in-Time User Provisioning

When a user accesses REANA for the first time, they may have no database entry, either because the IdP user identifier is not yet stored or because the user record has never been created.

Onboarding used to rely on custom synchronization scripts that imported user data in advance, but this proved asynchronous and hard to scale. To address this, it was implemented Just-in-Time [9] (JIT) provisioning for REANA: on the first request that contains a valid JWT, the server extracts the IdP identity, queries the OpenID UserInfo endpoint for minimal profile data, creates the user, stores `sub/iss`, and then continues the processing of the request (Figure 3).

Figure 3: JIT Provisioning

4.5 OAuth 2.0 Device Code Flow for the CLI

Historically, users supplied a token via an environment variable to CLI; the REANA team proposed moving to device code (Figure 4). With OAuth, the CLI, which is constrained interface environment, can authenticate using the device code flow, but the CLI must first discover which IdP a REANA deployment trusts.

To avoid hardcoding `reana-client` IdP values, REANA Server provides a proxy to the IdP’s OpenID configuration. When the user runs the CLI login, the CLI queries REANA Server, obtains the device authorization URL (“device code URL”), token URL, and `client_id`, and then starts the device code flow against the appropriate IdP. This centralizes IdP configuration, supports multiple REANA setups, and replaces the ad-hoc token provisioning with a standard, user-friendly login (Figure 5).

```

REANA Client OAuth

reana-client login

1) Go to:
https://iam-escape.cloud.cnaf.infn.it/device
2) Enter this code:
*****

Or open this link directly:
https://iam-escape.cloud.cnaf.infn.it/device?user_code=*****
Waiting for you to authorize..

=> SUCCESS: Login successful - token saved.
    
```

Figure 4: REANA Client Device Code

Figure 5: REANA Client IdP Payload

4.6 VRE-REANA Integration and Token Injection

The VRE maintains identity context and propagates credentials to user tools, e.g., Rucio for CLI access, by injecting them into the runtime environment. JupyterLab sessions are run as Kubernetes containers; on spawn, custom hooks inject a JWT access token as an environment variable.

For the REANA CLI, the token is also written to the `$HOME/.reana` config file. Then `reana-client` reads this file and uses the token for API calls automatically, without the need of a manual login from the user. For the REANA JupyterLab extension, the token remains available via the environment; the extension handlers read and store it to perform authenticated requests. The flow is summarized in Figure 6.

Figure 6: VRE Token Injection

4.7 Implementation Phases

This plan was created at the start of the project to manage dependencies, reduce integration risk, and enable smooth adoption.

- **Parallel Authorization Hooks.** JWT-based authorization runs in parallel with the legacy path while authorization hooks and OpenAPI updates land first; this provides a stable backend contract for tokens, enables iterative testing and feedback without disruption, and lays the groundwork for all clients.
- **CLI Device Flow After Backend.** Client-side authentication (device flow) is enabled once the server reliably validates tokens, avoiding circular dependencies and allowing clean, independent testing.
- **JIT Provisioning Introduced Later.** Just-in-Time user creation is added after JWT validation is stable; existing sync scripts remain temporarily to ensure onboarding continuity and de-risk the switch.
- **JupyterLab Extensions & Other Clients Updated Last.** The JupyterLab extension and other services update only after server and CLI support are solid; this prevents cascading failures, and no custom `reana-client` is required in the VRE because token injection with the standard client is already in place.
- **Optional Keycloak Integration.** Provide an optional IdP for sites without an institutional provider, improving portability without blocking core delivery.
- **Communication and Deployment.** Supply documentation, operator playbooks, and rollout guidance to support predictable adoption.
- **Invenio Authentication Removal.** Retire legacy components and related schema only after the new path is proven in production, closing the loop safely.

5 Future

Several improvements remain outside the scope of this work but are considered relevant for future development and operational adoption. The following items outline main phases that build on the current design and extend its capabilities.

- **Multi REANA Server configurations in the CLI:** Support selecting and managing multiple REANA Server targets within the CLI, enabling seamless context switching across deployments.
- **Refresh tokens on clients:** Introduce refresh tokens so that frontends and CLI can renew access tokens without user interaction, reducing re-authentication and improving session continuity.
- **Optional Keycloak integration in deployments:** Offer Keycloak as an optional IdP within the REANAHub stack for sites without an institutional provider, enabling standards-based login out of the box.
- **Multi-IdP support:** Generalize configuration for multiple trusted IdPs (including correct JWK selection and discovery), and provide user-facing selection where necessary.
- **Caching IdP JWKs:** Cache JWK sets locally with sensible TTLs to reduce network calls and improve authorization performance while respecting key rotation.
- **Scope-based access authorization:** Map REANA roles/permissions to OAuth 2.0/OIDC scopes to enable fine-grained, claim-driven authorization across services and tools.

6 Conclusion

REANA authentication was modernized within the ESCAPE Virtual Research Environment to rely on OIDC identity providers with server-side JWT verification, yielding a stateless, authorization-focused architecture. The change simplifies access, particularly through an easier CLI device authorization flow, and prioritizes maintainability and portability to accommodate diverse deployments and phase out aging packages. The platform is now aligned with federated identity practices and positioned for scope-aware policies and multi-IdP expansion.

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